

Using TROPOMI to map change in NO₂ over India in covid-19

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ABSTRACT: The novel coronavirus was first detected in Wuhan city of China in December 2019. The virus spread was exponential as it spread from China to European cities and then engulfed the whole world. To prevent the spread of coronavirus, the government of India announced a total lockdown on March 25, 2020. The regulations that required people to stay at home suspended all industry and transport. These measures reduced NO₂ from anthropogenic sources drastically, leading to a significant reduction in tropospheric NO₂ during covid[1].

The goal of this study is to

- a) Assess the NO₂ concentration over India using sentinel 5-p
- b) Identify the hotspots of air pollution due to NO₂

The reduction due to natural causes is assumed to be negligible as there was no significant change in natural conditions for 2020.

INTRODUCTION: Nitrogen dioxide is an essential trace gas and is found in the troposphere and stratosphere. NO₂ in the atmosphere can be attributed to natural as well as anthropogenic sources. The high concentration of NO₂ is mainly from fossil fuels, biomass burning and industry. The primary sources of NO₂ are the thermal power plants which emit copious amounts of NO₂. Nitrogen dioxide is a pollutant in the atmosphere, and at high concentrations, it combines to form HNO₃, NH₄NO₃[2]. The HNO₃ is the major cause of acid rain. In the troposphere, NO₂ direct poses problems to human health as a high concentration of nitrogen dioxide is known to cause respiratory problems[3].

The distribution of NO₂ in the troposphere is variable because of variable sources and the short lifetime of NO₂. Therefore it becomes essential to study the spatiotemporal variation of NO₂ for planning and management as it can be used to identify the source of pollution.

- 1.1) Remote Sensing of NO₂: Remote sensing of NO₂ via satellites has become one of the most crucial techniques of observation. Satellite remote sensing provides us with continuous data all around the globe at a reasonable accuracy. Remote sensing is not only helpful in monitoring NO₂, but it also helps to study NO₂

transport and sources of emission[4]. Today NO₂ products are available from Ozone Monitoring Instrument (OMI by NASA), Tropospheric Monitoring Instrument (TROPOMI by ESA). The data from such satellites are subject to errors associated with clouds, aerosols and inversion algorithms; therefore, it becomes vital to flag the data with low quality and secondly doing an error analysis to check the accuracy of derived data. The ground-based datasets are provided by several government agencies which set up air quality data stations in important tactical places, which can then be used to validate the satellite-derived data. The latest TROPOMI data has been found to have better accuracy than previous instruments[5].

- 1.2) TROPOMI NO₂: TROPOMI or Tropospheric Monitoring Instrument is a sensor onboard Sentinel 5P, a precursor satellite to Sentinel 5. It has a sun-synchronous orbit dedicated to monitoring air quality. It has eight spectral bands in UV, visible, NIR and SWIR. With its bands, it can determine the concentration of O₃, NO₂, CO, CH₄, SO₂, HCHO and aerosol properties. The sentinel 5P has a heritage with both OMI and SCIAMACHY and is used in tandem with both to provide a continuous time series of air quality data.

The data derived from sentinel 5P is the vertically integrated number of NO₂ molecules per unit area in the tropospheric region. The algorithm for inversion, which provides the Sentinel 5P level 2 data, is developed in[6]. The quality control for the cloud has to be done before analysis, and sentinel 5P provides a quality assurance flag. According to official documentation [6], the values of flag is 0.75 to remove problematic areas and errors.

Since it is difficult to remove the tropospheric NO₂ concentration from stratospheric NO₂ concentration due to variation of the tropopause, the DOMINO algorithm used by sentinel 5P uses data assimilation to generate final data [6]. Therefore this study uses only data assimilated offline products, which are more accurate and include some ground-based datasets.

METHODOLOGY:

The data is batch downloaded from sentinel hub. Sentinel hub provides an efficient way to batch download the scripts from <https://scihub.copernicus.eu/>.

Since the area of India is covered in 3 swaths by sentinel, the batch downloading is used to download the data for a month's duration and saved it in a folder. The methodology is described below

The code is available at (<https://github.com/der-knight/sentinel5p-NO2>). Sentinel provides the shell file to batch download the data. We need to give our inputs for a specific area to get files

HARP: HARP toolbox is designed to work with atmospheric data[7]. It is used to ingest process and compare atmospheric satellite data. The tool can be used in Python and MATLAB. With an appropriate HARP command line, satellite data can be pre-processed and correlated such that the final data has the same spatial, temporal and grid format for comparison and manipulation. Sentinel files are single files. HARP tool can be used to

spatially and temporally merge along with pre-processing. Once the existing grids are made every day, we can merge and create a final averaged map.

The latitude and longitude are used to confine the single orbit files spatially. According to official documentation, the tropospheric validity is a quality flag that has to be greater than 75 for values to be valid. HARP also generates a weight map, which is the number of values used to generate the average map. If weight shows low confidence, fewer values were used to generate the map; hence the average might not be as accurate as other places having high weight.

RESULTS:

Fig 2: Single sentinel swath over India

Fig3: NO₂ concentration in January

Fig 4 : NO₂ concentration in July

Fig 5: NO₂ concentration in October

Fig 5: Weight of NO₂ values in Feb

Fig 6: Weight of NO₂ values in July

The results are divided into two categories

- 1) The NO₂ concentration: Figure 3,4,5 show the NO₂ concentration variation over India. In January, we see a high concentration of NO₂ over India in Delhi and parts of NCR, Mumbai, and Jharkhand and Chhattisgarh (industrial areas). The NO₂ concentration then decreases as we move towards July and then starts increasing from October.
- 2) The Weight of NO₂: The weight is a depicter of the number of values taken to map NO₂ for that particular month. Since a quality flag for clouds is adopted, cloudy images are not taken for evaluation. High values of weight depict cloud-free images the whole month. There are even pixels where no image is available the whole month and is depicted by a zero pixel.

DISCUSSION: Coronavirus had a significant impact on emissions reductions as the lockdown was imposed starting in March. There have been various ground as well as satellite-based studies conducted to report a decrease in NO₂ levels [1][8][9][10]. All these studies report the immediate effect of a decrease in NO₂ concentration in the coming months. This study is more comprehensive, using high-resolution TROPOMI data to map a decrease in concentration over a more extended period and check the retrieval quality by presenting the number of data points available per month. This way, the impact of monsoon on satellite-based air quality retrieval can be identified.

Hotspot Identification: In January (Fig 3), we can identify the hotspots of NO₂ production over India during regular times. The red colour showing high concentration is present in thermal power plants of Odisha, Chhattisgarh and Madhya Pradesh. Other major emission hotspots are the megacities, mainly Delhi and Mumbai. Despite the municipal efforts, these cities have exceeded the air quality standards mainly due to fossil fuel emission. The hotspots due to the coal-based power plants remain during the lockdown as the electricity production is continued, as shown by the satellite imagery. There is a decrease in NO₂ concentrations over Jharkhand and other industrial areas as the metal industry was also under lockdown.

NO₂ Reduction: There is a decrease of about 50% in NO₂ concentration in megacities as there is a decrease in vehicular traffic, as can be seen from the satellite imagery. The major industries were also closed, leading to a decrease in emissions. In normal circumstances, a significant reason for an abrupt increase in NO₂ levels is stubble burning, leading to an increase in NO₂ levels. Due to the covid lockdown, there was a decrease in the number of fire activities which are generally done during the peak summertime, which a constant decrease in NO₂ levels can verify. Satellite imagery shows a decreasing trend in NO₂ levels all over India except northeast India, where there was the presence of forest fires.

Satellite retrievals during monsoon: Indian monsoon starts in July and overall lasts till September. Due to the clouds, there is a significant decrease in the number of observations per month available for generating the NO₂ data. This can be seen in the weights of NO₂, where the number of available samples early in the year is large, but in the months of July, August September is less. There are even data gaps in data for the above months. There is a subsequent increase in the number of data points from October.

NO₂ during Diwali: Diwali in 2020 was celebrated on November 14. Diwali is commonly associated with the burning of crackers. Although recently there has been a focus on a decrease in crackers, there is still a significant increase in concentration, as shown by the average NO₂ concentration between 12nov to November 17. Since the time frame is small, the data gaps are evident, albeit the high concentration of NO₂ is still visible along with the increase in concentration due to the loosening of norms. The data looks like it is moving towards pre covid level.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Biswal *et al.*, “COVID-19 lockdown induced changes in NO₂ levels across India observed by multi-satellite and surface observations,” *Atmos. Chem. Phys. Discuss.*, no. 2, pp. 1–28, 2020, doi: 10.5194/acp-2020-1023.
- [2] C. Wang, T. Wang, P. Wang, and V. Rakitin, “Comparison and Validation of TROPOMI and OMI NO₂ Observations over China,” *Atmosphere (Basel)*, vol. 11, no. 6, p. 636, Jun. 2020, doi: 10.3390/atmos11060636.
- [3] “Air quality guidelines. Global update 2005. Particulate matter, ozone, nitrogen dioxide and sulfur dioxide,” Mar. 2017, Accessed: January 02, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.euro.who.int/en/health-topics/environment-and-health/air-quality/publications/pre2009/air-quality-guidelines.-global-update-2005.-particulate-matter,-ozone,-nitrogen-dioxide-and-sulfur-dioxide>.
- [4] S. Beirle, K. F. Boersma, U. Platt, M. G. Lawrence, and T. Wagner, “Megacity emissions and lifetimes of nitrogen oxides probed from space,” *Science (80-.)*, vol. 333, no. 6050, pp. 1737–1739, Oct. 2011, doi: 10.1126/science.1207824.
- [5] D. Griffin *et al.*, “High-Resolution Mapping of Nitrogen Dioxide With TROPOMI: First Results and Validation Over the Canadian Oil Sands,” *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, vol. 46, no. 2, pp. 1049–1060, Jan. 2019, doi: 10.1029/2018GL081095.
- [6] J. H. G. M. Van Geffen, H. J. Eskes, K. F. Boersma, J. D. Maasakkers, and J. P. Veefkind, “TROPOMI ATBD of the total and tropospheric NO₂ data products,” 2019.
- [7] “HARP.” <https://atmospherictoolbox.org/harp/> (accessed January 04, 2021).
- [8] Z. S. Venter, K. Aunan, S. Chowdhury, and J. Lelieveld, “COVID-19 lockdowns cause global air pollution declines,” *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.*, vol. 117, no. 32, pp. 18984–18990, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.1073/pnas.2006853117.
- [9] N. Sahani, S. K. Goswami, and A. Saha, “The impact of COVID-19 induced lockdown on the changes of air quality and land surface temperature in Kolkata city, India,” *Spat. Inf. Res.*, pp. 1–16, Nov. 2020, doi: 10.1007/s41324-020-00372-4.
- [10] D. Singh, M. Dahiya, H. Space, A. Centre, and C. Nanda, “Geospatial View of Air Pollution and Health Risk over North Indian Region in COVID-19 Scenario,” doi:

10.21203/rs.3.rs-115247/v1.

Appendix 1: The full code can be found at <https://github.com/der-knight/sentinel5p-NO2>

Appendix 2: NO2 files and weight files from Jan to October

S-5p L2 NO₂ FEBRUAY 2020

S-5p L2 NO₂ APRIL 2020

5-5p L2 NO₂ MAY 2020

5-5p L2 NO₂ JUNE 2020

S-Sp L2 NO₂ JULY 2020

S-5p L2 NO₂ AUGUST 2020

S-5p L2 NO₂ SEPTEMBER 2020

S-Sp L2 NO₂ OCTOBER 2020

S-Sp L2 NO₂ diwali 2020

Weight- feb2020

Weight- APR2020

Weight- JUNE2020

Weight- AUG2020

Weight- SEP2020

Weight- OCT2020

Weight- diwali2020

